

On a Q-Smarandache Fuzzy Commutative Ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra

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Abstract

In this paper, the notions of Q-Smarandache fuzzy commutative ideal and Q-Smarandache fuzzy sub-commutative ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-Algebra are introduced, examples and related properties are investigated. Also, the relationships among these notions and other types of Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-Algebra are studied.

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1 Introduction

The concept of BCK-algebra was introduced by Y. Imai and K. Iseki [18]. In 1995 the concept of n-fold commutative BCK-algebras has been introduced [7]. In 1998, Y.B. Jun, E.H. Roh and H.S. Kim introduced the

notion of BH-algebra, which is a generalization of BCH/BCI/BCK-algebra [15]. In 2005, Y.B. Jun introduced the notion of a Smarandache BCI-algebra, Smarandache ideal of a Smarandache BCI-algebra [13]. In 2009, A.B. Saeid and A. Namdar, introduced the notion of a Q-Smarandache BCH-algebra and Q-Smarandache ideal of Q-Smarandache BCH-algebra [1]. In 2015, H.H. Abbass and H.K. Gatea introduced the notion Q-Smarandache Sub-Commutative ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-Algebra [4]. In this paper we introduce the notion of Q-Smarandache fuzzy Commutative ideal and Q-Smarandache fuzzy Sub-Commutative ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-Algebra. In this paper X denotes Q-Smarandache BH-Algebra.

2 Preliminary Notes

In this section, some basic concepts about a BH-algebra, a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra, a Q-Smarandach ideal in ordinary and fuzzy sences, Q-Smarandache sub-commutative ideal and Q-Smarandache commutative ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra are given.

Definition 2.1. [14]. A BCI-algebra is an algebra $(X, *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$, where X is a nonempty set, $*$ is a binary operation and 0 is a constant, satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- i. $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- ii. $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- iii. $x * x = 0$,
- iv. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

Definition 2.2. [11]. BCK-algebra is a BCI-algebra satisfying the axiom: $0 * x = 0$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition 2.3. [15]. A BH-algebra is a nonempty set X with a constant 0 and a binary operation $*$ satisfying the following conditions:

- i. $x * x = 0, \forall x \in X$.
- ii. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y, \forall x, y \in X$.
- iii. $x * 0 = x, \forall x \in X$.

Definition 2.4. [2]. A BCK-algebra X is called commutative if $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x), \forall x, y \in X$.

Lemma 2.5. [2]

In a BCI-algebra X the following conditions are equivalent:

- i. $x * y = x * (y * (y * x)), \quad \forall x, y \in X.$
- ii. X is a commutative BCK-algebra

Definition 2.6. [6]. A Q-Smarandache BH-algebra is defined to be a BH-algebra X in which there exists a proper subset Q of X such that

- i. $0 \in Q$ and $|Q| \geq 2.$
- ii. Q is a BCK-algebra under the operation of $X.$

Definition 2.7. [4] A Q-Smaradache BH-algebra is said to be a Q-Smaradache implicative BH- algebra if it satisfies the condition, $(x*(x*y))*(y*x)=y*(y*x).$
 $\forall x, y \in Q$

Definition 2.8. [4] A Q-Smarandache BH-algebra X is called a Q-Smarandache medial BH-algebra if $x * (x * y) = y, \forall x, y \in Q$

Definition 2.9. [6]. A nonempty subset I of X is called a Q-Smarandache ideal of X , denoted by a Q-S.I of X if it satisfies:

- (J_1) $0 \in I.$
- (J_2) $\forall y \in I$ and $x * y \in I \implies x \in I, \forall x \in Q.$

Definition 2.10. [4].A subset I of a BH-algebra X is called commutative ideal of X if it satisfies (J_1) and :

- (J_3) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I \implies x * (y * (y * x)) \in I, \forall x, y, z \in X.$

Definition 2.11. [4]. A subset I of a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra X is called a Q- Smarandache commutative ideal of X if it satisfies (J_1) and :

- (J_4) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I \implies x * (y * (y * x)) \in I, \forall x, y \in Q$ and $z \in X.$

Definition 2.12. [4].
 A nonempt subset I of a Q-Smarandache BH -algebra X is called a Q-Smarandache sub-commutative ideal of X if it satisfies (J_1) and :

- (J_6) $(y*(y*(x*(x*y))))*z \in I$ and $z \in I$ imply $x*(x*y) \in I, \forall x, y \in Q, z \in X$

Definition 2.13. [12] A fuzzy subset A of a BH-algebra X is said to be a fuzzy ideal if and only if:

$$(I_1) \quad A(0) \geq A(x), \forall x \in X.$$

$$(I_2) \quad A(x) \geq \min\{A(x * y), A(y)\}, \forall x, y \in X.$$

Definition 2.14. [16] Let X be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy set A in X is called a fuzzy commutative ideal of X if it satisfies (I_1) and

$$(I_3) \quad A((x * (y * (y * x)))) \geq \min\{((x * y) * z), (z)\} \quad \forall x, y, z \in X.$$

We generalize the concept of a Q-Smarandache fuzzy commutative ideal to the Q-Smarandache BH-algebra.

Definition 2.15. A fuzzy subset A of a BH-algebra X is called a fuzzy commutative ideal of X , denoted by a F.C.I if it satisfies (I_1) and

$$(I_4) \quad A((x * (y * (y * x)))) \geq \min\{((x * y) * z), (z)\} \quad \forall x, y, z \in X.$$

Definition 2.16. [10]. Let A be a fuzzy set in X , $\forall \alpha \in [0, 1]$, the set. $A_\alpha = \{x \in X, A(x) \geq \alpha\}$ is called a level subset of A . Note that, A_α is a subset of X in the ordinary sense.

Definition 2.17. [6]. A fuzzy subset A of X is said to be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X , denoted by a Q-S.F.I of X :

$$(F_1) \quad A(0) \geq A(x), \forall x \in X.$$

$$(F_2) \quad A(x) \geq \min\{A(x * y), A(y)\}, \forall x, \in Q, y \in X.$$

3 Main results

In this section, we introduce the concepts of a Q-Smarandache fuzzy commutative ideal and Q-Smarandache fuzzy sub-commutative ideal of a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra, and also we study some properties of them.

Definition 3.1. A fuzzy subset A of a X is called a Q-Smarandache fuzzy commutative ideal of X , denoted by a Q-S.F.C.I if it satisfies (F_1) and,

$$(F_3) \quad A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{A((x * y) * z), A(z)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Q, z \in X.$$

Example 3.2. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with binary operation "*" defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	3
1	1	0	2	3
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	3	0

where $Q = \{0, 1\}$ is a BCK-algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by $A(0) = A(1) = A(2) = 0.6$ and $A(3) = 0.3$.

Proposition 3.3. Every Q-S.F.C.I of X is Q-S.F.I of X

Proof. Let A be Q-S.F.C.I of X ,to prove that A is a Q-S.F.I. by Definition (3.1) the condition (F₁) is satisfied .Now, let x ∈ Q and y ∈ X. we have x = x * (0 * (0 * x))it follows that A(x) = A(x * (0 * (0 * x))) ≥ min{A(x * 0) * y), A(y)}[by 0*x=0 and x * 0 = x] implies that A(x) ≥ min{A(x * y), A(y)}. Hence A is Q-S.F.I of X. ■

Remark 3.4. In the following example, we see that the converse of theorem 3.3 may not be true in general.

Example 3.5. Consider X = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4} with binary operation "*" defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	0	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Where Q={0,2,3} is a BCK-algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by A(0) = 0.7, A(1) = 0.5 and A(2) = A(3) = A(4) = 0.3 A is a Q-S.F.I of X, but A is not a Q-S.F.C.I since if if x=2, y=3, z=0, then

$$A(2 * (3 * (3 * 2))) = 0.3 \not\geq \min\{A((2 * 3) * 0), A(0)\} = 0.7$$

Theorem 3.6. Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X. Then A is a Q-S.F.C.I of X if and only if the level subset A_αis a Q-S.C.I of X, ∀ α ∈ [0, A(0)], such that A(0) = sup_{x∈X} A(x)

Proof. Let A be a Q-S.F.C.I of X and α ∈ [0, A(0)]. To prove A_α is a Q-S.C.I of X.It is clear that A(0) ≥ α . So 0 ∈ A_α. Hence A_α satisfies I₁ .Now, let x, y ∈ Q, z ∈ X such that (x * y) * z ∈ A_α and z ∈ A_α, it follows that A((x * y) * z) ≥ α and A(z) ≥ α thus min{A((x * y) * z), A(z)} ≥ α. But A(x * (y * (y * x))) ≥ min{A((x * y) * z), A(z)} [Since A is a Q-S.F.C.I of X. By definition 3.1(F₃)] so A(x * (y * (y * x))) ≥ α ⇒ (x * (y * (y * x))) ∈ A_α Therefore, A_α is a Q-S.C.I of X.

Conversely,

Let A_α be a Q-S.C.I. of X, and ∀ α ∈ [0, A(0)]. It is clear that A(0) ≥ A(x) ∀ x ∈ X. Now, Let x, y ∈ Q, z ∈ X α = min{A((x * y) * z), A(z)} .Then A((x * y) * z) ≥ α and A(z) ≥ α , it follows that ((x * y) * z) ∈ A_α and z ∈ A_α, thus (x * (y * (y * x))) ∈ A_α[Since A_α is a Q-S.C.I of X] ⇒ A(x * (y * (y * x))) ≥ α, we get A(x * (y * (y * x))) ≥ min{A((x * y) * z), A(z)}. Therefore, A is a Q-S.F.C.I of X. ■

Proposition 3.7. *Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X .Then A is a Q-S.F.C.I if and only if $\forall x, y \in Q; A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq A(x * y)$ (b₁)*

Proof. Let A be a Q-S.F.C.I.Then $A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{A((x * y) * 0), A(0)\}$. [By definition3.1(F₃)]. We obtain $A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq A(x * y)$ [Since $x * 0 = x$ and $A(0) \geq A(x) \forall x \in X$]. Hence the condition (b₁) is satisfied

Conversely,

Let A be a Q-S.F.I and $x, y \in Q, z \in X$.Then $A(x * y) \geq \min\{A(x * y) * z, A(z)\}$ [A is a Q-S.F.I] $\Rightarrow A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{A(x * y) * z, A(z)\}$ [By condition (b₁)]. Therefore, A is a Q-S.F.C.I of X . ■

Theorem 3.8. *Let A be a Q-S.F.I of a commutative Q- Smarandache BH-algebra X such that Q is a commutative BCK-algebra . Then A is a Q-S.F.C.I of X.*

Proof. Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X.To prove that A is Q-S.F.C.I. By Definition (2.17) the condition (F₁) is satisfied. Now, let $x, y \in Q$ and $z \in X$. Then $A(x * y) \geq \min\{A((x * y) * z), A(z)\}$ [From Definition 2.17(F₂)] implies that $A(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{A((x * y) * z), A(z)\}$ [Since Q is commutative BCK-algebra,by Lemma 2.5(i)].HenceA is a Q-S.F.C.I of X. ■

Definition 3.9. *Let n be a positive integer. A nonempty subset I of X is called a Q-Smarandache n-fold commutative ideal of X. denoted by a Q-S .n-fold C.I of X if it satisfies (J₁) and :*

$$(J_5) (x * y^n) * z \in I \text{ and } z \in I \Rightarrow x * (y^n * (y^n * x)) \in I, \forall x, y \in Q \text{ and } z \in X.$$

Example 3.10. *Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with binary operation "*" defined by the following table:*

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	2	4	0

where $Q=\{0,1\}$ is a BCK-algebra . Then $I = \{0, 1, 2\}$ is A is a Q-S.2-fold.C.I

Definition 3.11. *Let n be a positive integer. A fuzzy subset A of a X is called a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold commutative ideal of X, denoted by a Q-S.F .n-fold.C.I of X if it satisfies (F₁) and,*

$$(F_4). A(x * (y^n * (y^n * x))) \geq \min\{A(x * y^n) * z, A(z)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Q, z \in X$$

Example 3.12. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with binary operation "*" defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	2	4	0

where $Q=\{0,1\}$ is a BCK-algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by $A(0) = A(1) = A(2) = 0.8$ and $A(3) = A(4) = 0.5$ A is a Q-S.F.2-fold.C.I.

Proposition 3.13. Every Q-S.n-fold.F.C.I of X is Q-S.F.I of X

Proof. let A Q-S.F.C.I of X To prove that A is Q-S.F.I. by Defintion (3.11) the condition (F_1) is satisfied .Now, let $x \in Q$ and $y \in X$. we have $x = (x * (0^n * (0^n * x)))$ it follows that $A(x) = A(x * (0^n * (0^n * x))) \geq \min\{A(x * 0^n) * A(y), A(y)\}$ [by $0 * x = 0$ and $x * 0 = x$] implies that $A(x) \geq \min\{A(x * y), A(y)\}$. Hence A is Q-S.F.I of X. ■

Remark 3.14. In the following example, we see that the converse of Proposition 3.13 may not be true in general.

Example 3.15. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with binary operation "*" defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	4
1	1	0	0	0	4
2	2	2	0	1	4
3	3	3	3	0	4
4	4	4	4	4	0

where $Q=\{0,1,2\}$ is a BCK- algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by $A(0) = 0.8$ and $A(1) = A(2) = A(3) = A(4) = 0.5$ Is Q-S.F.I of X, but it is not 1-fold Q-S.F.C.I of X. Since $x=1, y=2, z=0$

$$A(1 * (2 * (2 * 1))) = 0.5 \not\geq \min\{A((1 * 2) * 0), A(0)\} = 0.8$$

Theorem 3.16. Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X .Then A is a Q-S.F.n-fold C.I if and only if

$$\forall x, y \in Q, \quad A(x * (y^n * (y^n * x))) \geq A(x * y^n) \quad (b_2)$$

Proof. Let A be a Q-S.F.n-fold C.I of X and $x, y \in Q$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A(x * (y^n * (y^n * x)) &\geq \min\{A((x * y^n) * 0), A(0)\} \text{.[By definition 3.11 (F}_4\text{)]} \\
 \implies A(x * (y^n * (y^n * x)) &\geq A(x * y^n) \text{[Since } x * 0 = x, A(0) \geq A(x). \forall x \in X\text{]} \\
 \implies \text{The condition (b}_2\text{) is satisfied.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Conversely,

let A be a Q-S.F.I of X , $x, y \in Q$ and $x \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 A(x * y^n) &\geq \min\{A((x * y^n) * z), A(z)\} \text{[Since } A \text{ is a Q-S.F.I of } X \text{]} \\
 \implies A(x * (y^n * (y^n * x))) &\geq \min\{A((x * y^n) * z), A(z)\} \text{ [By condition(b}_2\text{)]}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, A is a Q-S.F.n-fold .C.I of X ■

Definition 3.17. A fuzzy subset A of X is called a Q-Smarandache fuzzy sub-commutative ideal of X , denoted by a Q-S.F.S.C.I of X if it satisfies (F_1) and,

$$(F_5) \quad A(x * (x * y)) \geq \min\{A(y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * z, A(z)\} \quad \forall x, y \in Q, z \in X.$$

Example 3.18. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with binary operation " $*$ " defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

where $Q = \{0, 1\}$ is a BCK-algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by $A(0) = A(1) = A(2) = 0.6$ and $A(3) = 0.3$ A is Q-S.F.C.I of X .

Theorem 3.19. Let A be a Q-S.F.S.C.I of X . Then A is a Q-S.F.I of X .

Proof. Let A be a Q-S.F.S.C.I of X . It is clear that the condition (F_1) is satisfied. Now, let $x \in Q$ and $y \in X$, we have $A(x * (x * x)) \geq \min\{A(x * (x * (x * (x * x))) * y), A(y)\}$, [By Definition 3.17(F_5)] it follows that $A(x * 0) \geq \min\{A(x * (x * (x * 0) * y), A(y)\}$ [Since Q is a BCK-algebra $x * x = 0$] implies that $A(x) \geq \min\{A(x * y), A(y)\}$ [Since Q is a BCK-algebra $x * 0 = x$]. Hence A is a Q-S.F.I of X . ■

Remark 3.20. In the following example shows that the converse of theorem 3.19 may not be true in general.

Example 3.21. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with binary operation " $*$ " defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	2	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Where $Q=\{0,1,2\}$ is a BCK-algebra. The fuzzy subset A defined by $A(0) = A(3) = 0.9$, and $A(1) = A(2) = 0.5$ A is a Q-S.F.I of X , but it is not a Q-S.F.S.C.I. Since, $x=1, y=2, z=0$

$$A(1 * (1 * 2)) \not\geq \min\{A(2 * (2 * (1 * (1 * 2)))) * 0), A(0)\}$$

Theorem 3.22. Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X . Then A is a Q-S.F.S.C.I of X if and only if it is $\forall x, y \in Q, A(x * (x * y)) \geq A(y * (y * (x * (x * y))))$ (b_3)

Proof. Suppose A is a Q-S.F.S.C.I of X . Let $x, y \in Q$. Then $A(x * (x * y)) \geq \min\{A(y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * 0), A(0)\}$ [By definition 3.17(F_5)] it follows that $A(x * (x * y)) = \min\{A(y * (y * (x * (x * y))))), A(0)\}$ [Since $X ; x * 0 = x$] implies that $A(x * (x * y)) \geq A(y * (y * (x * (x * y))))$ [$A(0) \geq A(x) \forall x \in X$]. By definition 3.17(F_1)]. Hence The condition (b_3) is satisfied.

Conversely,

Let A be a Q-S.F.I of X and the condition (b_2) satisfied. To prove that A is Q-S.F.S.C.I. By Definition (2.17) the condition (F_2) is satisfied. Now, let $x, y \in Q$ and $z \in X$ we have $A(y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) \geq \min\{A(y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * z), A(z)\}$ [Since A is a Q-S.F.I of X , by Definition 2.17 (F_2)] implies that $A(x * (x * y)) \geq \min\{A(y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * z), A(z)\}$ [By (b_3)]. Hence A is a Q-S.F. S.C.I of X . ■

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